

The Influence of Work Motivation and Work Environment on Employee Performance at the Labuhan Batu District Education Office with Work Discipline as Intervening Variables

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ABSTRACT: Human resources are very important for companies or government agencies in managing, organizing, and utilizing employees, so that they can function productively to achieve the goals of the company or government institution. Human resources in companies or government institutions need to be managed professionally in order to realize a balance between the needs of employees and the demands and capabilities of the company's organization. This study aims to determine whether work motivation and work environment affect employee performance through work discipline as an intervening variable at the Labuhanbatu District Education Office. The study was conducted on 61 employees using saturated sampling techniques. The data collection techniques used are primary data in the form of questionnaires and secondary data obtained through documentation studies. The data analysis technique uses quantitative data processed with the SPSS version 25 program, namely t test, sobel test and path analysis. The results obtained in this study show that 1) there is a significant influence between work motivation on work discipline, 2) there is a significant influence between work environment variables on work discipline, 3) there is a significant influence between work motivation variables on performance, 4) there is a significant influence between work environment variables on performance, 5) there is a significant influence between work discipline variables on performance, 6) work discipline variables cannot affect work motivation variables to performance, 7) work discipline variables cannot affect work environment variables to performance.

KEYWORDS: Performance, Work Motivation, Work Environment, Work Discipline.

INTRODUCTION

Human resources are one of the resources that exist in a company or government institution in addition to other resources, such as capital, materials, machinery and technology. Human resources are very important for companies or government agencies in managing, organizing, and utilizing employees, so that they can function productively to achieve the goals of the company or government institution. In a company or government institution, the problem of managing employees professionally must begin since employee recruitment, selection, classifying, placement of employees according to their abilities, upgrading, and career development have become commonplace. Companies or government agencies should consider carefully and carefully, as they relate to the overall operation and viability of the company or government agency. The Education Office of Labuhan Batu Regency is a government implementing unit in the field of education under the auspices of the local government. Led by a Head of Service who will be responsible to the Regent/Governor through the Regional/Regional Secretary of the Province. The Education Office of Labuhan Batu Regency actually only expects the best achievements or work results from its employees. The phenomenon in the Education Office of Labuhan Batu Regency, there are differences in organizational expectations and reality in the field. Employee performance is still considered less than optimal, it is characterized by a decrease in work results achieved from some employees, especially in carrying out work. Based on the results of research, the decline in performance is influenced by employee work discipline that has not been created properly. The existence of work discipline is also very important, because with a disciplined work atmosphere an office can carry out the planned work program. Work discipline is a mental or group attitude that is always willing to follow and obey all the rules that are set. In general, high performance is associated with high motivation. In contrast, low motivation is associated with low performance. High performance is the functioning and interaction between motivation, competence and opportunities of supporting resources. Motivation can also be defined as an act to influence others to behave regularly. Motivated employees will give rise to a good spirit of work discipline and also affect the improvement of employee performance in the organization. With strong motivation, the thrust is also strong to improve employee performance. The work environment is one of the important factors in improving employee performance, because the work environment has a direct influence on employees in completing work which will ultimately

have a strong effect on performance that produces achievements. Seeing the importance of the influence of work motivation and work environment on employee performance, it is appropriate that work motivation for employees and a comfortable work environment are provided by every organization, both private organizations and government organizations. Based on the phenomenon that occurred at the Labuhan Batu Regency Education Office, researchers were interested in conducting a study related to this phenomenon with the title "The Effect of Work Motivation and Work Environment on Employee Performance at the Labuhan Batu District Education Office with Work Discipline as an Intervening variable".

LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance

Performance is a real behavior that everyone displays as work achievements produced by employees according to their role in the agency. Performance is very important in the agency's efforts to achieve its goals.

There are factors that come from within one's own human resources as well as from outside oneself. The factors that affect performance according to Sutrisno (2011: 176-177) include:

1. Effectiveness and efficiency
2. Authority and responsibility
3. Discipline
4. Initiatives

Performance indicators according to Kasmir (2016: 208), can be used several indicators regarding performance criteria, namely: "quality, quantity, timeliness, cost-effectiveness, need for supervision, and relationships between individuals. It is this indicator that will be the benchmark in measuring performance".

Work Discipline

Discipline is the ability to master oneself and carry out the norms prevailing in common life. Work discipline can be seen if employees come to the office regularly and on time, if they dress neatly at work, if they use office supplies well, if they produce a satisfactory amount and quality of work by following a predetermined way of working and if they complete work on time.

With the established rules, the employees will not obey them by themselves. It is necessary for the agency to condition its employees with the existing rules in the agency.

There are factors that influence discipline, (Singodimedjo in Agustini, 2011: 80) are as follows :

1. Presence/absence of Leadership Supervision
2. Presence/Absence of Exemplary Leaders in the Organization
3. Courage of the Leader and Taking Action
4. Presence/Absence of Attention to Employees
5. The Creation of Habits That Support the Establishment of Discipline

There are several indicators of discipline according to Agustini (2011: 73) which are as follows:

1. Attendance rate, which is the number of employee attendance to carry out work activities in the office which is characterized by a low level of employee absenteeism.
2. Working procedures, namely rules or conditions that must be obeyed by all members of the organization.
3. Obedience to the superior, that is, following what the superior directs in order to get good results.
4. Awareness works, that is, the attitude of a person who voluntarily does his task well not by coercion.
5. Responsibility, namely the willingness of employees to account for their work results, the facilities and infrastructure used, and their work behavior.

If the employee has embedded the five indicators above, then an employee has reflected good discipline and is responsible for the tasks assigned to him.

Work Motivation

Motivation is an activity that results in a person completing their work with enthusiasm, willingness and full of responsibility. Motivation serves as a driver or encouragement to employees to be willing to work hard for the achievement of agency goals properly.

Below are some of the factors that affect work motivation according to experts. According to Frederick Herzberg in Noor (2013: 250) divided into two factors, namely as follows:

1. Motivation factor. Which is a motivating factor for a person to excel which comes from within that person (intrinsic condition), including:

- a. Achievements achieved
- b. Recognition of others
- c. Responsibility
- d. Opportunities to advance
- e. Job satisfaction itself
- f. Career development possibilities

2. Maintenance factor. Which is a factor related to the fulfillment of the need to maintain the existence of employees as human beings, the maintenance of peace and health. Those that are qualified into extrinsic factors, include:

- a. Compensation
- b. Occupational security and safety
- c. Working conditions
- d. Status
- e. Corporate procedures
- f. The quality of technical supervision of interpersonal relationships between peers, with superiors, and with subordinates.

Motivation is a factor that drives a person to do a certain activity. The indicators of work motivation according to Mangkunegara (2017: 111) include:

1. Hard work, that is, carrying out activities with all the abilities possessed.
2. Future orientation, that is, interpreting what will happen in the future and planning for it.
3. A high level of ideals, that is, to have better ambitions.
4. Task / goal orientation, that is, always oriented towards quality work results.
5. Effort to advance, that is, to carry out activities to obtain goals.
6. Perseverance, that is, to do all work diligently and earnestly.

Working Environment

The work environment is a place where employees carry out activities every day. A conducive work environment provides a sense of security and allows employees to be able to work optimally. The work environment can affect the emotionality of employees. If the employee likes the work environment in which he works, then the employee will feel at home in his workplace, carrying out his activities so that work time is used effectively. A working environment condition is said to be good or appropriate if humans can carry out activities optimally, healthy, safe and comfortable.

Factors affecting the physical work environment according to Sedarmayanti (2013:26) is :

1. Lighting/lighting at work
2. Humidity in the workplace
3. Noise at work
4. Smells at work
5. Color layout at work
6. Decoration at work
7. Music at work
8. Safety at work

In measuring work environment variables, there are several indicators, this study dimensions and indicators adapt according to Sedarmayanti (2013: 26):

1. Dimensions of the Physical Work Environment

With the following indicators:

- a. Lighting

- b. Air circulation
- c. Noise
- d. Space for Movement
- e. Facilities
- f. Hygiene
- g. Color
- h. Music
- i. Privacy

METHODOLOGY

This research is included in associative research with a quantitative approach. This study examined the relationship between the variables Work Motivation (X1) and Work Environment (X2) to the variables Performance (Y) with Work Discipline (Z) as intervening variables. In this study, the approach used is a quantitative approach because the data used to analyze the influence between variables is expressed by numerical numbers or scales (Kuncoro, 2011, in Wulandari, 2015). The research was conducted at the Education Office of Labuhan Batu Regency which is located at Jalan Menara, No. 7, Rantauprapat, Labuhan Batu Regency, North Sumatra. Meanwhile, the research time was carried out from October 2022 to January 2022.

The data collection techniques used are:

1. Questionnaire, by making a list of questions in the form of a questionnaire addressed to employees.
2. Documentation studies, by collecting data on companies or agencies related to research needs.

The procedures in this study are as follows:

1. Preliminary Stage, namely determining the location of the study, identifying the problem, limiting the problem, formulating the problem, collecting literature, compiling questionnaires, and testing the validity and reliability of the questionnaires used.
2. Implementation Stage, namely distributing questionnaires to be filled out by respondents, processing data and then analyzing data.
3. Reporting Stage, which is to write and compile a research report in the form of a thesis.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Sub Model I Test Results

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	46,365	7,078		6,550	,000
Work Motivation	,115	,129	,116	2,892	,006
Work Environment	,143	,107	,173	2,330	,009

a. Dependent Variable: work discipline

In the table, a statistical test t is obtained, as follows :

- 1) Work Motivation Variable (X1) with a probability level of 0.006. Thus it can be concluded $P = 0.006 < \alpha = 0.05$, accept the hypothesis that states work motivation has a significant effect on the variables of work discipline.
- 2) Working Environment Variable (X2) with a probability level of 0.009. Thus, it can be concluded that $P = 0.009 < \alpha = 0.05$, then accept the hypothesis that states that work environment variables have a significant effect on work discipline variables.

Thus can be compiled the path analysis equation as follows :

$$Z = 0.116 X1 + 0.173 X2$$

The analysis equation model means:

1) Work Motivation Variable (X1) = 0.116 A positively marked work motivation variable means that it has a unidirectional influence, which means that any addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the work motivation variable will add a work discipline variable value of 0.116 per one unit score.

2) Working Environment Variable (X2) = 0.173. A work environment variable that is positively marked means that it has a unidirectional influence, which means that every addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the work environment variable will increase the value of the work discipline variable by 0.173 per one unit score.

Thus obtained the path diagram of the structure model I as follows:

B. Sub Model II Test Results

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	61,555	14,778		4,165	,000
Work Motivation	,167	,205	,108	3,817	,018
Work Environment	,045	,173	,035	3,259	,007
Work Discipline	,200	,208	,128	3,963	,040

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Source : Primary Data Processed, 2022

On the table, a statistical test t is obtained, as follows:

1) Work Discipline Variable (Z), with a probability rate of 0.040. Thus it can be concluded $P = 0.040 < \alpha = 0.05$, then accept the hypothesis that states the variable of work discipline has a significant effect on performance.

2) Work Motivation Variable (X1), with a probability level of 0.018 Thus it can be concluded $P = 0.018 < \alpha = 0.05$, then accept the hypothesis that states the work motivation variable has a significant effect on performance.

3) Work Environment Variable (X2), with a probability level of 0.007. Thus it can be concluded $P = 0.007 < \alpha = 0.05$, then accept the hypothesis that states the variables of the work environment have a significant effect on performance.

Thus can be compiled the path analysis equation as follows:

$$Y = 0.108 X_1 + 0.035 X_2 + 0.128 Z$$

The analysis equation model means:

1) Work Motivation Variable (X1) = 0.108. A positively marked work motivation variable means that it has a unidirectional influence, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the work motivation variable will increase the value of the performance variable by 0.108 per one unit score.

2) Working Environment Variable (X₂) = 0.035. A work environment variable that is positively marked means that it has a unidirectional influence, which means that every addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the work environment variable will increase the value of the performance variable by 0.035 per one unit score.

3) Work Discipline Variable (Z) = 0.128. A work discipline variable that is positively marked means that it has a unidirectional influence, which means that every addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the work discipline variable will increase the value of the performance variable by 0.128 per one unit score.

C. Sobel Test

The following are the results of the sobel test with variables of work motivation towards performance through work discipline.

$$t = \frac{0.116 \times 0.128}{\sqrt{(0.128^2 \times 0.129^2) + (0.116^2 \times 0.208^2)}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.116 \times 0.128}{\sqrt{0.00027264614 + 0.00058216038}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.014848}{0.00085480652}$$

$$t = 17.370$$

From the results of the calculation of the sobel test above getting a t value of 17,370, so that a calculated t value of 17,370 > t table 3,887 was obtained, it can be concluded that the work discipline variable is able to mediate the relationship of the influence of work motivation on performance.

The following are the results of the sobel test with work environment variables on performance through work discipline.

$$t = \frac{0.173 \times 0.128}{\sqrt{(0.128^2 \times 0.129^2) + (0.173^2 \times 0.107^2)}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.173 \times 0.128}{\sqrt{0.00027264614 + 0.00034265712}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.022144}{0.00061530326}$$

$$t = 35.988$$

From the results of the calculation of the sobel test above, it gets a t value of 35,988, so that a calculated t value of 35,988 > t table of 3,887 is obtained, it can be concluded that the work discipline variable is able to mediate the relationship of the influence of the work environment on performance.

Thus obtained the path diagram of the structure model II as follows :

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Work Motivation on Work Discipline

The variable of work motivation has a positive and significant effect on work discipline at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The work motivation variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.116 has a unidirectional effect, which means that every addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the work motivation variable will increase the work discipline value of Labuhanbatu Education Office employees by 0.116 per one unit score.

The Effect of Work Environment on Work Discipline

Work environment variables have a positive and significant effect on work discipline at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The work environment variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.173 has a unidirectional effect, which means that every addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the work environment variable will increase the work discipline value of Labuhanbatu Education Office employees by 0.173 per one unit score.

The Effect of Work Motivation on Performance

The variable of work motivation has a positive and insignificant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The work motivation variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.108 has a unidirectional effect, which means that every addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the work motivation variable will increase the performance value of labuhanbatu education office employees by 0.108 per one unit score.

The Effect of Work Environment on Performance

Work environment variables have a positive and insignificant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The work environment variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.128 has a unidirectional effect, which means that every addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the work environment variable will increase the performance value of the Labuhanbatu Education Office by 0.128 per one unit score.

The Effect of Work Discipline on Performance

The variable of work discipline has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The work discipline variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.035 has a unidirectional influence which means that every addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the work discipline variable will increase the performance value of labuhanbatu education office employees by 0.035 per one unit score.

The Effect of Work Motivation on Performance through Work Discipline

Based on the results of the sobel test calculation, it is known that the t value is 17,370, so that the calculated t value of 17,370 > t table 3,887 is obtained, it can be concluded that the work discipline variable is able to mediate the relationship of the influence of work motivation on performance. And based on the track analysis, it is known that the magnitude of the influence of work motivation (X1) on the performance (Y) of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office is 12%, which consists of a direct influence of 10.8% and an indirect influence of Work Motivation (X1) on Performance (Y) through Work Discipline (Z) of 0.12%. The results of this calculation show that the direct influence of Work Motivation (X1) on Performance (Y) is greater than its indirect influence. Thus it can be said that work motivation is effective in improving performance, in other words it can be affirmed that Work Motivation (X1) has an influence if there is an increase in employee performance in carrying out duties.

The Effect of the Work Environment on Performance through Work Discipline

Based on the results of the calculation of the sobel test, it is known that the t value is 35,988, so that the calculated t value of 35,988 > t table 3,887 is obtained, it can be concluded that the work discipline variable is able to mediate the relationship of the influence of the work environment on performance. And based on the track analysis, it is known that the magnitude of the influence of the Work Environment (X2) on the Performance (Y) of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office is 13%, which consists of a direct influence of 12.8% and an indirect influence of the Work Environment (X2) on Performance (Y) through Work Discipline (Z) of 0.2%. The results of this calculation show that the direct influence of the Work Environment (X2) on Performance (Y) is greater than its indirect influence. Thus it can be said that the influence of the Work Environment (X2) will be less likely to improve Performance (Y) if it is carried out through Work Discipline (Z).

CONCLUSION

a. Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on work discipline at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. This means that this condition proves that providing work motivation can improve employee work discipline.

b. The work environment has a positive and significant effect on work discipline at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. This means that this condition proves that the existence of a good work environment can improve employee work discipline.

c. Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. This means that this condition proves that providing work motivation to employees can improve performance.

d. The work environment has a positive and significant effect on the performance of the Labuhanbatu Education Office. This means that this condition proves that the existence of a good work environment can improve employee performance.

e. Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. This means that this condition proves that the higher the work discipline can improve performance.

f. The effect of work motivation on the performance of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office will be smaller if it is carried out through work discipline. The direct influence of work motivation on employee performance is greater than the indirect influence of work motivation on performance. It can be concluded that work discipline is not able to mediate the influence of work motivation on performance.

g. The effect of the work environment on the performance of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office will be smaller if it is carried out through work discipline. The direct influence of the work environment on performance outweighs the indirect influence of supervision on performance. It can be concluded that work discipline is able to mediate the influence of the work environment on performance.

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